

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 32

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 32

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 32:0 <i>A Psalm</i> of David. A †Maskil.</p>	<p>Psa. 32:1 לְדָוִד מִשְׁכִּיל אֲשֶׁר־</p>
<p>Psa. 32:1 "How blessed is he whose transgression is forgiven, Whose sin is covered!</p>	<p>נְשׁוּי־פָשַׁע כְּסִי־חַטָּאת : 2 אֲשֶׁר־יָאֵם לֹא יִחַשֵׁב יְהוָה לוֹ</p>
<p>² How blessed is the man to whom the LORD "does not impute iniquity, And in whose spirit there is ^bno deceit!</p>	<p>עוֹן וְאֵין בְּרוּחֹו רְמִיָּה : 3 כִּי־ הִחַרְשֵׁתִי בְּלוֹ עֲצָמַי בְּשִׂאֲנֹתַי</p>
<p>Psa. 32:3 When "I kept silent <i>about my sin</i>, ^bmy ¹body wasted away Through my ²groaning all day long.</p>	<p>כָּל־תְּיוֹם : 4 כִּי אִיזְמָם וְלִילָה תִּכְבֵּד עָלַי יָיָךְ נִהַפְךָ לְשִׁרֵי</p>
<p>⁴ For day and night "Your hand was heavy upon me; My ¹vitality was drained away <i>as</i> with the fever heat of summer. ²Selah.</p>	<p>בְּחִרְבְּנֵי קִיץ סָלָה : 5 חַטָּאתַי אוֹדִיעֶךָ וְעוֹנִי לֹא־כִסִּיתִי</p>
<p>⁵ I "acknowledged my sin to You, And my iniquity I ^bdid not hide; I said, "I will confess my transgressions to the LORD"; And You ^dforgave the ¹guilt of my sin. Selah.</p>	<p>אִמְרֹתַי אוֹדָה עָלַי בְּשָׁעֵי לִיהוָה וְאַתָּה נָשֵׂאתָ עוֹן חַטָּאתַי סָלָה : 6 עַל־זֹאת יִתְפַּלֵּל כָּל־תְּסִיד אֵלֶיךָ לְעֵת</p>
<p>⁶ Therefore, let everyone who is godly pray to You ^{1a}in a time when You may be found; Surely ^bin a flood of great waters they will not reach him.</p>	<p>לְמַצָּא רֶק לְשִׁטְף מַיִם רַבִּים אֵלָיו לֹא יִגִּיעוּ : 7 אֲתָה וְסִתַּר לִי מִצָּר תִּצְרַנִּי רַגְלֵי פִלֵּט</p>
<p>⁷ You are "my hiding place; You ^bpreserve me from trouble; You surround me with ^{1c}songs of deliverance. Selah.</p>	<p>תִּסּוּבְּבֵנִי סָלָה : 8 אֲשַׁכִּילְךָ וְאוֹרְךָ בְּדַרְךָ־זוֹ תִלְךָ אֵי־עֵצָה עָלֶיךָ עֵינַי : 9 אֶל־תִּהְיוּ וּכְסוּסִים</p>
<p>Psa. 32:8 I will "instruct you and teach you in the way which you should go;</p>	<p>כְּפָרָד אֵין הָבִין בְּמִתְגַּוְרָסִין עֲדִינוּ לְבָלוֹם בְּלִ קָרַב אֵלֶיךָ :</p>

<p>I will counsel you ^bwith My eye upon you.</p> <p>⁹ Do not be ^aas the horse or as the mule which have no understanding, Whose trappings include bit and bridle to hold them in check, <i>Otherwise</i> they will not come near to you.</p> <p>¹⁰ Many are the ^asorrows of the wicked, But ^bhe who trusts in the LORD, lovingkindness shall surround him.</p> <p>¹¹ Be ^aglad in the LORD and rejoice, you righteous ones; And shout for joy, all you who are ^bupright in heart.</p>	<p>¹⁰ רַבִּים מִכְּאַזְבִּים לְרָשָׁע</p> <p>וְהַבֹּשֶׁת בֵּיתוֹהָ חֶסֶד יִסּוּבְבָנָיו :</p> <p>¹¹ שְׂמְחוּ בַּיהוָה וְגֵילוּ צְדִיקִים</p> <p>וְהִרְנְנוּ כָּל-יִשְׂרָאֵל-לֵב :</p>
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References

<p>Psalm 32:0 ¹Possibly <i>Contemplative, or Didactic, or Skillful Psalm</i></p> <p>Psalm 32:1 ^aPs 85:2; 103:3; Rom 4:7, 8</p> <p>Psalm 32:2 ^a2 Cor 5:19 ^bJohn 1:47</p> <p>Psalm 32:3 ¹Or <i>bones, substance</i> ²Lit <i>roaring</i> ^aPs 39:2, 3 ^bPs 31:10 ^cPs 38:8</p> <p>Psalm 32:4 ¹Lit <i>life juices were turned into the drought of summer</i> ²<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo or Musical interlude</i> ^a1 Sam 5:6; Job 23:2; 33:7; Ps 38:2; 39:10 ^bPs 22:15</p> <p>Psalm 32:5 ¹Or <i>iniquity</i> ^aLev 26:40 ^bJob 31:33 ^cPs 38:18; Prov 28:13; 1 John 1:9 ^dPs 103:12</p>	<p>Psalm 32:6 ¹Lit <i>in a time of finding out</i> ^aPs 69:13; Is 55:6 ^bPs 46:1-3; 69:1; 124:5; 144:7; Is 43:2</p> <p>Psalm 32:7 ¹Or <i>shouts</i> ^aPs 9:9; 31:20; 91:1; 119:114 ^bPs 121:7 ^cEx 15:1; Judg 5:1; Ps 40:3</p> <p>Psalm 32:8 ^aPs 25:8 ^bPs 33:18</p> <p>Psalm 32:9 ^aProv 26:3</p> <p>Psalm 32:10 ^aPs 16:4; Prov 13:21; Rom 2:9 ^bPs 5:11, 12; Prov 16:20</p> <p>Psalm 32:11 ^aPs 64:10; 68:3; 97:12 ^bPs 7:10; 64:10</p>
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Targum

Psa. 32:1 Of David. Good counsel. David said, "How blessed is the one whose impieties they forgive, whose sins they cover over." ² How happy was Moses, son of Amram, to whom the LORD did not reckon his sins, because there was no guile in his spirit. ³ Because I have been silent from the words of Torah, my bones waste away while I groan all day. ⁴ Because day and night your punishment is severe upon me, my moisture is turned to, as it were, the hot wind of summer forever. ⁵ My sin I will tell you and my iniquity I have not covered. I said, "I will confess my rebellions in the presence of the LORD"; and you forgave the iniquity of my sin forever. ⁶ Because of this let every pious man pray in your presence at the time of his favor; indeed, at the time when many Gentiles come like waters, to him they will not come near to do harm. ⁷ You are the LORD; hide me, from the oppressor guard me; the joy of salvation will surround me forever. ⁸ I will enlighten you and teach you; in this way you shall go; I will advise you and put my eye upon you for good. ⁹ Do not be like a horse or mule who have no intelligence; both muzzle and halter are its trappings to be kept silent; let it not come near you. ¹⁰ Many are the pains of the wicked; but favor will surround the one who trusts in the LORD. ¹¹ Rejoice in the word of the LORD, and be glad, O righteous; and give praise, all you with upright hearts.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This is the first Psalm of David that addresses repentance. David explains that repentance is more than simply attaining Divine forgiveness. All types of repentance bring about at least some forgiveness. The soul cannot be returned to its state before a sin was created unless the heart is cleansed and the spirit is properly conditioned. The highest level of purity and forgiveness is achieved on Yom Kippur (Leviticus 16:30).

Superscript

מִשְׁכִּיל (mas'ceel) – means "poem." The psalms that have this word in their superscript contain an instructive lecture or explanation.

A Maskil by David

Verse one

אַשְׁרֵי נַשׂוּי (ash'rai n'soo) – means "blessed forgiven." When these two words are combined in verse, it means "raised above and tested against transgression." Happy is the person who is tried against transgressions and is protected from sin. Our own moral energy is adequate to help us to remain free from transgressions.

"The words 'sin' and 'transgression' are used synonymously on many occasions, yet there is also a difference in their meanings. We know that to sin is to break a law of God, but to transgress may mean to go beyond a limit. In fact, the word *transgress* comes from the Latin *transgredior*—*trans* meaning *beyond*, and *gredior*, meaning *to pass*.

To sin is to break the moral code; to transgress could be to violate a law without sinful intent. As an example, a person intentionally breaking the speed limit while driving a car on the freeway could be classed as committing a sin against the laws of the State, while a policeman exceeding the speed limit while chasing a criminal would have transgressed the speed limit law, but having done so in the performance of duty for a noble purpose, would not be punished for breaking the law against speeding."¹

Happy is the person who is tried against transgression and protected from sin.

Verse two

David admits that he did not always feel that he had attained the spiritual height of being without iniquity.

Happy is the person in whom the LORD sees no iniquity and in whose spirit there is no deceit.

¹ "What Is the Difference between a Sin and a Transgression?," Ask Gramps - Q and A about Sin and Transgression, September 29, 2021, <https://askgramps.org/what-is-the-difference-between-a-sin-and-a-transgression/>.

Verse three and four

David's sins had caused him to have physical suffering.

For when I kept silent, my bones wore away through my groaning all day long.

For day and night, Your hand lay heavily upon me; my marrow was turned as in the droughts of the heat of summer. Meditate on this verse.

Verse five

In this verse, David believed that the LORD removed the iniquity of his sins even before he confessed the sins.

LORD, you had already removed the iniquity of my sin before I admitted it to you. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

Material suffering is a means to send a message from the LORD to awaken the proper spiritual life in the soul. Suffering is represented by the allegory of floodwaters. This is probably because of the flood during Noah's time.

Therefore, let every one of devotion seek clarity of judgment before You at the time of affliction. The mighty flood of great waters will not reach him to wash away sins.

Verse seven

You are a shade to me even then, You preserve me from distress, You cause the rejoicing of deliverance to encompass me. Meditate on this verse.

Verse eight

אֲשַׁכֵּילְךָ (as'keel'cha) – literally it means "I shall permit you to employ your mind for intelligent perception and reasoning. In other words, I shall cause you to engage in rational contemplation.

I shall instruct you and teach you how you are to go; I would advise you from my own experience.

Verse nine

The Psalmist implores us not to be like dumb animals. People are always to show that they are a human beings with intelligence gifted to us by the LORD.

Don't be like a horse or mule that is devoid of intelligence. It is their mark that must be restrained by the bit or bridle so that they will not come near to you.

Verse ten

There are sufferings in the world that are intended solely for people who will not submit to the authority of the LORD's Law. People who sin and seek forgiveness from the LORD through repentance will be sheltered by His love.

Many sufferings are intended only for the lawless who don't follow the LORD's Law, but as for persons who trust in the LORD, the LORD will surround that person with mercy.

Verse eleven

All people who place their faith and trust in the LORD will rejoice and shout for joy.

Therefore, be glad in the LORD, and rejoice with great joy for all who are righteous, and let those who are upright in heart be of good cheer.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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